

MANUFACTURING AND IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH EMBEDDED GRAPHENE PLATELETS

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Abstract:

Sandwich composites have been considerably used in the aerospace and marine industry for their light-weight and excellent structural, energy absorption and impact resistance properties. Additionally, recent advancements in nano-reinforced materials have allowed enhancement and tailoring of the mechanical and impact properties of resulting composites. In this work, sandwich composites comprising of glass-fiber face sheets and PVC foam were manufactured using vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. Nano-graphene platelets were strategically placed in the external layers of the face sheets. The resulting sandwich structures were subjected to varying impact loads and their behavior was compared with pristine samples. Dye-penetration tests were performed to study the extent of damage. Graphene-embedded specimens showed significantly less damage than pristine samples impacted to similar energy level. Overall, results show great promise in tailoring the impact behavior of sandwich composites through strategic placement of graphene nano-reinforcements.

1 Introduction

Composite sandwich structures have found extensive applications in aerospace, marine, wind and ground vehicle industries due to their high specific strength and stiffness, high resistance to impact and energy absorption properties [1-5]. Considerable work on sandwich structures that utilize various cores such as honeycomb, balsa and foam exists and an excellent review on sandwich structures and their low-velocity impact behavior is provided in [6]. Polymeric foams derived from materials such as polyvinylchloride (PVC), polyurethane (PU), polyethylenterephthalate (PET), expanded polystyrene slabs (EPS), etc. are gaining attention as the core material for sandwich structures for variety of applications [3-5]. A wide range of thermo-mechanical characterization and

resulting properties of sandwich structures are possible depending on the materials used, their configurations and testing schemes.

In spite of many advantages offered by these high-performance sandwich composite structures, their susceptibility to localized impact loads is of concern [5-6]. Specifically, low-velocity impacts result in a barely visual damage that can go undetected but can compromise the resulting structural properties and premature failure. Damage can occur in the facings, core or core-face interface [5-6] and the extent of damage depends on many factors including properties of face sheets, core, and the relationship between the properties of the cores, facings size and shape of the structure [5].

Recent advancements in nano-reinforced materials have allowed enhancement and tailoring of the mechanical and impact properties of resulting composites. Of particular interest is the addition of exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets to the polymer matrix has been shown to produce nanocomposites with enhanced mechanical and multifunctional properties [7-12]. An excellent review on the graphene based materials is provided in [9] and the energy absorption in generic nanocomposites is provided in [10]. The use of nanoparticles in sandwich structures has recently gained considerable interest [13-15]. The use of nanoclay [13-15] and graphene [13,14] has been shown to improve energy absorption in sandwich structures. Similarly, in a parallel effort by the authors, the use of graphene nanoplatelets to improve impact resistance in monolithic composites [11] and resulting joints [16] had shown reduction in the through-thickness damage, and this work aims at extending the knowledge into sandwich composites.

In this work, impact behavior of sandwich composites comprising of S2-glass-fabric face sheets, PVC foam core and graphene nanoplatelets

on face sheets was studied. The manufacturing, materials used, nanocomposite processing, experimental methods and resulting performance are provided in the following sections.

2 Materials and Experimental Procedures

2.1 Materials

The materials used in the study were as follows. Owens Corning ShieldStrandS, S2-glass plain weave fabric with an areal weight of 818 g/m² was used as face-sheet reinforcement. DIAB[®] Divinycell [17] non porous H130 PVC foam with a thickness of 25.4 mm was used as the core material. The distribution medium was AIRTECH Advanced Materials Group Resinflow 60 LDPE/HDPE blend fabric. The resin was Applied Poleramic SC-15 two-phase epoxy cycloaliphatic amine with an ambient viscosity of 0.35 Pa.s. The nano-reinforcement was untreated exfoliated graphite nanoplatelet (xGnP) prepared at Michigan State University. The diameter of the nanoplatelet was 5µm and the thickness was ~7nm.

2.2 xGnP Coating Process

Solutions of 2 wt% xGnP in 2-propanol were prepared. The solutions were mixed using both a mechanical stirring device and a sonicator. The S-2 glass fabrics were cut to the desired dimensions and weighed. Measured amounts of the xGnP 2-propanol solution was then poured onto the surface of the glass fabric and brushed until it was evenly distributed. The coated fabrics were placed beneath a fume hood until the 2-propanol was evaporated. Samples were prepared with 1.0 wt% xGnP coated on one surface of the glass fabric. All impact tests were performed on the face sheet with GnP coating.

2.3 Resin Infusion

A steel mold (609.6mm x 914.4mm) with point injection and point vent was used to fabricate 304.8mm x 609.6mm sandwich panels. A schematic of the VARTM layup scheme is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Layup for the VARTM process

The upper face sheet consisted of either four plies of the “as received” glass fabric or four plies of the

glass fabric coated with xGnP nanoplatelets. The lower face sheet used four plies of the “as received” glass fabric. Two layers of resin distribution medium were used over the top face sheet and one sheet was used the beneath the bottom face sheet. This was done to equalize the resin infiltration times for the top and bottom face sheets.

Once all the materials were laid, the mold was sealed using a vacuum bag and sealant tape. The vacuum was drawn and the mold was infused. The resin infused sandwich panel was cured in a convection oven at 60°C for 2h and post cured at 94°C for 4h.

2.4 Impact Testing

A drop weight instrumented impact test system was used to test the composite specimens under low impact velocities. The machine setup consists of an instrumented tup (12 mm diameter) mounted on a crosshead with a provision for attachment of varying weights. The crosshead slides along stiff, smooth guide columns. The specimen was clamped at the base of the machine in a fixture that has circular support. Sample sizes of 10 cm x 10 cm were used for the test. Energy of impact was varied by varying the drop height. The samples (with and without graphene in the face-sheets) were subjected to impact at four different energy levels 40, 60, 80 and 100 J. For GnP coated specimens, the face sheet with GnP was placed upward to come in contact with the tup / projectile during the impact.

3 Results

A total of eight samples were tested under low-velocity impact conditions at 40, 60, 80, and 100 J. At each energy level, a sandwich specimen with and without graphene coating on the face sheet was tested. The impact system used in this work provides load, energy and displacements as a function of time for each of the samples tested. The extent of impact damage in the various samples was evaluated by both visual inspection and UV-dye penetration tests.

In the current study, the impact phenomenon is characterized in terms of peak load and absorbed energy. Energy absorption in composites is mainly through two modes: elastic strain energy and through various damage modes. The composite laminates are brittle in nature and respond elastically

until peak load [12]. If the impact energy is higher than the energy absorbed until the peak load, the additional energy is taken up in the creation of damage. Figure 2 provides the impact response for pristine (no xGnP) sandwich samples at varying energies. It is commonly agreed that the impact parameters can be related to peak load. In general, it was observed that the total energy and deflection at peak load increase with increasing energies while the time to reach peak load decreases. Also, absorbed energy which is measured as the difference between the total applied energy and the energy at peak load increases with an increase in applied impact energies.

Figure 2 Impact response of pristine (no xGnP) sandwich panels at varying impact energies

Figure 3. Impact response of xGnP sandwich panels at varying impact energies.

It can be observed from Figure 2, that the slope of the load-time plot and the peak load value increases with increase in impact energy. At higher energy levels (>40 J), we observe oscillations, and the load-time plot becomes asymmetric about the peak load, indicating the onset and propagation of damage. At energies greater than 40J, the load reaches a peak

value followed by a sudden drop indicating a perforation in the top skin of the face sheet. Also, the asymmetry in the load-time curve and the elongated unloading region indicates that the foam is undergoing deformation and taking some part of the load. Similar results have also been reported in [5].

Figure 3 provides the impact response at varying energies for sandwich specimen with graphene coating on the face sheet experiencing the impact loads. The load-time histories were found to be symmetric for both 40J and 60J indicating minimal impact damage in the sample. It should be noted that damage and asymmetry in load-time curve was observed at 60J for pristine sandwich specimens. This indicates the nano-graphene placement in the facesheet has resulted in enhancement of impact properties and prevention of permanent or excessive damage. The area of damage for pristine and GnP samples for various energies is shown in Figure 4. It can be clearly seen for 60J sample that the extent of damage was relatively minimal compared to pristine sample (Figure 4b). Similar to pristine specimens, the load-time response at higher energies (80 J and 100 J) was asymmetric and unloading region was elongated. Similar results have been reported in [5].

In a parallel effort by the authors [11] on the study of impact behavior of monolithic glass fiber/SC-15 epoxy plates with graphene coated outer layers, it was found that with increasing impact energies the damage area increased laterally in the form of interlaminar damage in the outer plies that contained graphene. Minimal through thickness damage was observed [11] and the existence of layered graphene in the interlaminar layers was attributed to such behavior. In this study, the existence of energy absorbing foam structure provided additional impact resistance along with graphene. Figure 4 provides the extent of damage for pristine and graphene coated samples as obtained from UV dye penetration tests. It was observed that the area/extent of damage was lower in graphene coated samples relative to similar pristine samples. Furthermore, at high energies (100J), the projectile/tup caused puncture/through thickness damage of the outer plies of the sheet (Figure 4d). Such severe damage was not observed in graphene coated samples. The existence of graphene further enhances the impact properties of the sandwich structures.

Figure 4. UV dye penetration images showing the extent of damage in pristine and GnP coated samples at various impact energies

Overall, the study showed the potential of nanographene platelets in enhancing the impact/energy-absorption properties of sandwich structures. Nevertheless, further experiments with statistically significant number of tests along with varying amounts of graphene need to be performed to fully exploit the benefits offered by these novel materials. Additionally NDE techniques such as Ultrasonic scanning and microscopic evaluation of cross-sections need to be performed to fully understand the evolution and propagation of damage. Such work is in progress and will be communicated shortly.

4. Conclusions

Sandwich structures made of SC-15 woven glass fabric and PVC foam were manufactured with novel nanographene (GnP) platelets in the faces sheets and their impact behavior was evaluated. The effect of GnP on impact properties and reducing the extent of damage was studied by comparing with pristine (no GnP) samples. The sandwich panels were manufactured by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding process (VARTM) while the graphene nanoplatelets were coated/painted on the face sheet prior to infusion. The presence of graphene enhanced the energy absorption properties of the resulting sandwich panels. The sandwich panels with graphene were found to have less area of damage along with minimal through thickness damage and negligible perforation of face sheets. The study included a single concentration of graphene. Detailed studies including varying amounts of graphene, robust NDE techniques and statistically significant number of tests need to be performed to fully exploit the benefits offered by this novel material. Nevertheless, results from this work show great potential in the use of nanographene in enhancing and tailoring the impact properties of sandwich structures.

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